

Summary Paper on the Role of Institutional Regulatory and Legal Frameworks with concrete suggestions for enhancing policy coherence

MATS Deliverable 4.5

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

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Summary

This summary paper is part of Deliverable 4.5 of the Horizon 2020 MATS (Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable) project, which examines the impact of institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks on sustainable agricultural trade between the European Union (EU) and partner countries. The study synthesises findings from 15 case studies, focusing on how these frameworks influence trade dynamics, sustainability objectives, and policy coherence with global environmental and development goals.

The research highlights significant variations in how institutional frameworks affect agricultural trade across different regions and sectors. Case studies from countries like Tanzania, Uganda, and Ethiopia illustrate the challenges small-scale producers face in meeting EU standards for food safety, environmental and social sustainability. The high compliance costs and limited capacity for monitoring and enforcement in developing countries create significant barriers to market access, reinforcing existing inequalities.

One of the report's central themes is the role of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and its alignment with sustainability goals, particularly those set out in the European Green Deal. While the CAP promotes environmentally sustainable farming practices, the report identifies policy incoherencies, such as subsidies that encourage intensive farming, contradicting the EU's environmental objectives, impacting internal EU trade but also the EU's trade with African countries. Furthermore, gaps in addressing intellectual property rights and innovation in agricultural trade frameworks are noted as areas requiring more attention to support fair competition and sustainable development.

The paper underscores the need for better policy coherence between trade and environmental goals. Existing legal instruments, such as the General Food Law and the EU's Farm to Fork Strategy, have made strides in promoting sustainability. However, their uneven application across EU member states and partner countries poses challenges. Moreover, the limited enforcement of labour and human rights provisions in trade agreements weakens the effectiveness of EU policies in promoting social equity and sustainable development.

Some recommendations include enhancing the alignment of EU policies with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), strengthening the legal frameworks governing agricultural trade, and improving coordination mechanisms among EU institutions, member states, and international partners. The report also advocates for greater support for capacity-building in developing countries to ensure that small-scale producers can benefit from trade relationships with the EU.

The summary paper has focused on policy coherence with respect to the role of institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks in promoting policy coherence, complementing the analysis of agreements and political initiatives that make up the core trade policy of the EU (D4.2.), and in conclusion calls for more integrated and coherent policy approaches to address the complex interplay between trade, sustainability, and development. By aligning its trade policies more closely with global environmental and social goals, the EU can enhance its role as a leader in promoting sustainable agricultural practices and fair trade globally.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background and Importance of Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development

Policy coherence is vital for achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs), particularly in agricultural trade, environmental sustainability, and climate action. The European Union (EU) has committed to promoting policy coherence to ensure that its internal and external policies align with global sustainability objectives, including the SDGs and various environmental and climate agreements.

Policy coherence for sustainable development (PCSD) has emerged as a critical concept in the global policy agenda, particularly in achieving the SDGs. The SDGs, adopted by all United Nations member states in 2015, address various social, economic, and environmental challenges. 1. Achieving these goals requires coherent policies preventing conflicts between sectors and promoting synergies. This is especially important in trade policy, where decisions can have widespread effects on environmental sustainability, social equity, and economic development (OECD, 2023, 48-49).

The European Union (EU) has promoted policy coherence as a strategic approach to ensure that its internal and external policies align with the SDGs. The concept of PCSD goes beyond merely avoiding contradictions between policies; it actively seeks to maximise synergies across different policy areas to achieve sustainable development. This approach is essential for the EU, which plays a significant role in global trade and must ensure that its trade policies do not undermine its commitments to sustainability and development cooperation (Carbone, 2008, 325-326). Moreover, the EU's focus on 'Green Deal' initiatives further emphasises the need for coherent policies integrating environmental sustainability with economic growth (European Commission *EU Green Deal*, 2019).

However, achieving policy coherence is not straightforward. It involves navigating complex interactions between multiple stakeholders, including governments, international organisations, civil society, and the private sector. In trade and sustainability, policy coherence is challenged by conflicting objectives, such as economic growth versus environmental protection or trade liberalisation versus social equity. These conflicts can result in 'policy incoherence,' where actions in one policy domain undermine the objectives of another (Nilsson et al., 2012, 320). For example, while the EU promotes sustainable agricultural practices through its Common

Agricultural Policy (CAP), it has been criticised for trade policies that may incentivise unsustainable practices in partner countries.

Policy coherence is crucial in the agricultural sector, intersecting trade, environmental sustainability, and social development. The agricultural sector is a significant source of greenhouse gas emissions and a vital livelihood for millions of smallholder farmers worldwide. Incoherent trade policies can have severe implications for global environmental and social goals. The need for coherent policies is underscored by the MATS project, which highlights the impact of institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks on sustainable agricultural trade between the EU and its partners (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 2-3).

1.2. Objectives and Scope of the Discussion Paper

This discussion paper aims to synthesise the findings from analysing institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks that govern agricultural trade and sustainable development within the EU and its partner countries. It provides concrete suggestions for enhancing the EU's legal and institutional frameworks to promote policy coherence, particularly aligning policies with SDGs and global environmental and climate challenges agreements.

This discussion paper synthesises the main findings from an analysis of the role of institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks in promoting policy coherence, particularly concerning aligning these frameworks with the SDGs and global agreements on environmental and climate challenges. The EU's trade and sustainability policies are examined to understand the extent to which they are coherent and aligned with broader sustainable development objectives. This paper also provides concrete suggestions for enhancing the EU's legal and institutional frameworks to promote better policy coherence.

The scope of the discussion paper encompasses a review of key EU policies and frameworks that govern agricultural trade, environmental sustainability, and development cooperation. It also draws on insights from specific case studies within the MATS project, which analyse the impact of institutional frameworks on trade dynamics, particularly concerning compliance with EU regulations and international agreements (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 4). These case studies provide valuable evidence on the challenges and opportunities in aligning trade policies with sustainability objectives.

Moreover, the discussion paper addresses the gaps and incoherencies identified in current EU frameworks and offers recommendations for future policy directions. This includes exploring the need for more integrated approaches to policy formulation,

better coordination mechanisms among EU institutions, and increased support for capacity building in developing countries. The paper recognises the critical role of EU policies in shaping global trade practices. It underscores the importance of ensuring these policies contribute to sustainable development rather than undermining it (D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 6-7).

1.3. Methodology and Sources

The paper is based on analysing four key documents that provide insights into the role of legal frameworks in promoting sustainable agricultural trade and policy coherence. These documents include findings from the MATS project case studies and reports on policy coherence, trade regimes, and environmental sustainability. Each section of the paper references specific findings and recommendations from these documents to support the discussion.

This discussion paper is based on a qualitative analysis of various documents and case studies related to the EU's trade and sustainability policies. The primary sources include four critical documents provided by the MATS project, which offer a comprehensive overview of the role of institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks in promoting sustainable agricultural trade. These documents include (1) "The Political Economy of Trade Regimes," which examines the role of trade regimes in achieving sustainable agricultural practices (D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*); (2) The Report on the "Webinar 'Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development'," which provides insights from a hybrid workshop focusing on policy coherence in agricultural trade (D4.4); (3) 'Discussion Paper on Mechanisms that Can Ensure that EU Policies are Coherent with SDGs,' which offers a detailed analysis of the alignment between EU policies and SDGs (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*); and (4) 'Synthesis of Findings on the Impact of Institutional Frameworks from the Set of 15 Case Studies,' which synthesises the findings from case studies that examine the legal and institutional frameworks governing agricultural trade (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*).

The methodology involves synthesising findings from these sources to identify key themes and patterns related to policy coherence, regulatory frameworks, and sustainability. This approach comprehensively explains the challenges and opportunities in aligning EU policies with SDGs and global environmental agreements. The paper also includes concrete recommendations based on the analysis, focusing on enhancing the EU's legal and institutional frameworks to promote sustainable development.

1.4. Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in its contribution to ongoing debates on the role of trade policies in achieving sustainable development. By examining the EU's legal and institutional frameworks, this paper provides insights into current policies' effectiveness and identifies areas for improvement. It also highlights the importance of a coherent policy approach integrating trade, environmental sustainability, and social equity. This is particularly relevant in global challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and inequality, which require coordinated policy responses at all levels (Meadowcroft, 2007, 299-300).

The study also responds to the growing demand for evidence-based policy-making, particularly in sustainable development. As the EU continues negotiating trade agreements with various partners, ensuring these agreements align with broader sustainability goals is essential. This paper provides a valuable resource for policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders interested in understanding the complexities of trade and sustainability and developing more coherent and effective policy frameworks (Mayer & Gereffi, 2017).

1.5. Policy Context and Relevance

The relevance of this study is underscored by the ongoing policy discussions within the EU regarding the alignment of trade and sustainability policies. The European Green Deal, for instance, represents a significant step towards integrating sustainability into all policy areas, including trade. However, achieving the objectives of the Green Deal requires coherent policies that avoid contradictions and maximise synergies across sectors. This discussion paper aims to contribute to these discussions by providing a detailed analysis of the existing frameworks and suggesting ways to enhance policy coherence (European Commission, 2019).

Furthermore, the paper's focus on concrete recommendations for improving the EU's legal and institutional frameworks aligns with the EU's commitment to promoting sustainable development globally. As the EU seeks to position itself as a global leader in sustainability, it must ensure that its internal and external policies are coherent and contribute to achieving the SDGs. This paper offers practical insights and recommendations to help the EU strengthen its policy frameworks and enhance its impact on global sustainable development (Young & Peterson, 2013).

2. Role of Institutional, Regulatory, and Legal Frameworks in Promoting Policy Coherence

2.1. Overview of Institutional, Regulatory, and Legal Frameworks

The EU's institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks are crucial in shaping agricultural trade, ensuring food safety, promoting environmental sustainability, and aligning trade policies with global standards and agreements. Key frameworks include the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the General Food Law, regulations on organic production, environmental directives, and international agreements such as the Paris Agreement.

Institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks are essential for ensuring policy coherence, particularly when addressing complex global challenges such as sustainability, climate change, and equitable development. These frameworks encompass the rules, regulations, and standards set by governing bodies that shape the behaviour of economic actors, guide decision-making processes, and define the legal context within which trade and sustainability policies operate. These frameworks are particularly relevant at the European Union (EU) level due to the EU's significant influence on global trade policies, environmental standards, and development cooperation agreements (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 3-4).

A coherent institutional framework aligns the objectives of different policy areas to avoid conflicts and promote synergies, thus contributing to sustainable development. For instance, the EU has established numerous regulations under its Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), General Food Law, and the EU Green Deal. These aim to integrate environmental sustainability into agricultural practices, ensure food safety, and enhance market access for sustainably produced goods. However, these regulations must work harmoniously across sectors, such as trade, environment, and development cooperation, to effectively support the SDGs and international environmental agreements (OECD, 2018).

In addition to EU-specific regulations, international legal frameworks such as the World Trade Organization (WTO) agreements on Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures (SPS) and Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) play crucial roles in shaping global trade practices. These agreements establish standards that govern the safety

and quality of traded goods, thereby facilitating trade while protecting human, animal, and plant health. Integrating these global frameworks into EU policies is critical for ensuring that the EU's trade practices are aligned with international norms and support global sustainability objectives.

Voluntary standards and certifications, such as Fair Trade, Organic, and Rainforest Alliance, also facilitate institutional coherence. These standards encourage sustainable practices by providing market incentives for compliance, enhancing access to environmentally and socially conscious markets, and promoting sustainable development objectives. However, the effectiveness of such standards in fostering policy coherence depends on their integration with national and international legal frameworks and the support provided for compliance, particularly in developing countries (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 5-6; Mayer & Gereffi, 2017, 5).

2.2. The Role of EU Policies in Agricultural Trade and Sustainable Development

EU policies on agricultural trade are designed to promote sustainability, market access, and development cooperation with partner countries. However, achieving policy coherence requires these policies to align with SDGs and other global environmental and climate challenges agreements. The EU's legal instruments must ensure that trade does not undermine development objectives, environmental protection, and climate resilience.

The EU's policies on agricultural trade are pivotal in promoting sustainable development both within and outside its borders. As one of the largest agricultural importers and exporters globally, the EU has significant leverage in shaping global agricultural trade practices. EU policies like the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) are designed to support sustainable agricultural production by providing financial incentives for practices that protect the environment, enhance biodiversity, and reduce greenhouse gas emissions (European Commission *Farm to Fork*, 2020). The CAP also plays a crucial role in ensuring food security, maintaining rural livelihoods, and promoting economic growth in rural areas.

However, while the CAP promotes sustainability goals within the EU, its impact on partner countries can vary significantly. For example, trade agreements negotiated by the EU, such as Economic Partnership Agreements (EPAs) with African, Caribbean, and Pacific (ACP) countries, are intended to enhance trade relationships and promote development. However, these agreements have been criticised for not fully addressing partner countries' developmental needs or imposing challenging standards for small-scale producers (Carbone, 2008, 326). This inconsistency can

undermine the EU's broader objective of promoting sustainable development and policy coherence (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 5-6).

Furthermore, the European Green Deal, launched in 2019, has set a new paradigm for EU trade policy by emphasising climate neutrality and sustainability across all policy areas. The Green Deal's Farm to Fork Strategy aims to make food systems fair, healthy, and environmentally friendly, targeting reducing the use of pesticides, fertilisers, and antibiotics and promoting organic farming. While these objectives align well with SDGs, the challenge lies in ensuring that these policies do not adversely impact trade relationships, especially with developing countries that rely on agricultural exports to the EU market (European Commission *EU Green Deal*, 2019).

EU policies also play a critical role in addressing global environmental challenges. For example, the EU's commitment to the Paris Agreement requires aligning trade policies with climate goals. This involves reducing carbon emissions within the EU and ensuring imports from partner countries comply with environmental standards supporting climate action. The introduction of the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) reflects this approach by seeking to level the playing field for EU producers and prevent carbon leakage. However, such measures must be carefully balanced to avoid creating new barriers to trade that could negatively affect developing countries (Young & Peterson, 2013, 499-500).

In addition, the EU's efforts to promote policy coherence are evident in its development cooperation policies, which aim to integrate trade, environmental sustainability, and social development. The Policy Coherence for Development (PCD) agenda, now embedded within the broader concept of Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development (PCSD), reflects the EU's commitment to ensuring its policies support development objectives in partner countries. However, achieving coherence between trade and development policies requires more than aligning objectives; it involves addressing power asymmetries, enhancing institutional capacities, and ensuring that policy implementation supports rather than undermines sustainable development (Nilsson et al., 2012).

The European Union (EU) plays a pivotal role in shaping global agricultural trade and advancing sustainable development through various policies that address economic, social, and environmental dimensions. The **Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)** remains the EU's most influential policy framework for agriculture, having evolved over the decades to incorporate sustainability and environmental considerations. The CAP supports farmers through direct payments, market support measures, and rural development funding, aiming to ensure a stable food supply, preserve rural livelihoods, and protect the environment. However, while recent CAP reforms have introduced "greening" measures to promote sustainable farming practices, the policy

has faced criticism for not going far enough in aligning agricultural production with environmental and climate goals (European Commission *Farm to Fork*, 2020; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 3-5).

One significant challenge with the CAP is balancing productivity with sustainability. While the CAP's direct payments system encourages farmers to maintain land in good agricultural condition, it has also been criticized for favouring large-scale, intensive farming operations that can contribute to environmental degradation, such as soil erosion, loss of biodiversity, and water pollution. To address these issues, the latest CAP reforms for 2023-2027 introduce *Eco-schemes*, which provide financial incentives for farmers who adopt sustainable practices, such as organic farming, agroforestry, and precision agriculture. However, the success of these Eco-schemes will depend on their design, uptake, and implementation across member states, which vary widely in their agricultural practices and capacities (D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 5-6).

The **Farm to Fork Strategy**, part of the European Green Deal, is another key policy initiative to create a more sustainable food system in the EU by addressing issues across the entire food chain—from production and processing to distribution and consumption. This strategy sets ambitious targets, such as reducing the use of chemical pesticides by 50%, lowering fertilizer use by 20%, and increasing the share of organic farming to 25% of EU agricultural land by 2030. While these targets are aligned with broader sustainability goals, their implementation poses significant challenges, particularly for small-scale farmers who may struggle to adapt to new regulations and practices without adequate support (European Commission *EU Green Deal*, 2019; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 7-8).

Another critical policy affecting agricultural trade and sustainability is the **EU's Trade and Sustainable Development (TSD) Chapters**, which are included in Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) with partner countries. These chapters aim to integrate sustainability standards, such as labour rights and environmental protection, into trade relations. However, the effectiveness of TSD chapters is often limited by their reliance on dialogue and cooperation rather than binding commitments and enforcement mechanisms. Strengthening these chapters by incorporating legally enforceable provisions and robust monitoring systems could significantly enhance their impact on promoting sustainable agricultural trade (Young & Peterson, 2013, 501).

The **EU Organic Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2018/848)** is also crucial for promoting sustainable agricultural practices within the EU. This regulation sets standards for organic farming and production to increase consumer trust and support for organic products. By ensuring that organic products meet strict environmental, animal welfare, and food safety standards, the regulation helps to promote sustainable farming practices and enhance market access for organic farmers.

However, expanding organic farming also requires significant changes in supply chains, from input provision to processing and distribution, which may pose challenges for existing agricultural systems and require coordinated policy support (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 4; Mayer & Gereffi, 2017, 5).

Additionally, the **General Scheme of Preferences Plus (GSP+)** offers another layer of EU policy that affects agricultural trade and sustainable development. GSP+ provides tariff reductions for developing countries that commit to implementing international human rights, labour rights, environmental protection, and good governance conventions. While GSP+ is designed to promote sustainable development in partner countries, its impact has been mixed. Some argue that the scheme does not sufficiently address the structural challenges faced by small-scale producers, such as limited access to credit, technology, and markets, which are crucial for achieving meaningful improvements in sustainability (Carbone, 2008, 329; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 9-10).

The **EU's Biodiversity Strategy for 2030** also significantly shapes agricultural trade policies by aiming to halt biodiversity loss and promote sustainable land use. The strategy calls for protecting 30% of the EU's land and marine areas and restoring at least 10% of agricultural land to high-diversity landscapes. This policy directly affects agricultural trade, as it affects land use decisions, production practices, and the types of products that can be traded. However, balancing biodiversity conservation with agricultural productivity remains a contentious issue, as farmers must adapt to new constraints and find ways to maintain profitability while contributing to biodiversity goals (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 11-12).

The **Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)**, proposed under the European Green Deal, is another policy that impacts agricultural trade. While primarily aimed at sectors like steel and cement, CBAM can also affect agricultural trade by imposing carbon costs on imports that do not meet EU climate standards. Such a policy can incentivize partner countries to adopt greener agricultural practices to avoid tariffs, promoting sustainable development. However, implementing CBAM also raises concerns about its potential impact on trade relations, particularly with developing countries that may lack the capacity to rapidly transition to low-carbon agricultural practices (European Commission *EU Green Deal*, 2019; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 13).

The **Common Market Organization (CMO) Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 1308/2013)** provides a framework for managing EU agricultural markets and stabilizing prices, which is crucial for ensuring fair income for farmers and supporting rural development. The CMO Regulation includes measures to support specific sectors, such as fruits and vegetables, wine, and olive oil, through producer organizations and operational programs that promote sustainability. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of these measures depends on the capacity of producer

organizations to adopt sustainable practices and the availability of technical and financial support to facilitate this transition (European Commission, 2020; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 8-9).

Moreover, the **EU's Circular Economy Action Plan**, which aims to promote sustainable production and consumption patterns, significantly impacts agricultural trade between the EU and other countries. The action plan supports a more sustainable and resilient agricultural system by encouraging sustainable and circular agricultural practices—such as recycling organic waste, reducing food loss and waste, and promoting resource efficiency. However, integrating circular economy principles into agricultural trade requires substantial policy coordination across different sectors and targeted investments in research, innovation, and infrastructure (Mayer & Gereffi, 2017, 10; D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 5-6).

Finally, the **EU-Africa Strategy**, which seeks to enhance cooperation between the EU and African countries on trade, development, and climate action, also shapes agricultural trade policies. The strategy aims to promote sustainable agricultural value chains, improve market access for African agricultural products, and support climate-resilient farming practices. However, achieving these objectives will require addressing structural challenges, such as inadequate infrastructure, limited access to finance, and insufficient capacity for meeting EU standards. Enhancing support for capacity-building programs and fostering partnerships between EU and African stakeholders will ensure that agricultural trade contributes to sustainable development on both continents (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 14-15; Young & Peterson, 2013, 503).

The role of EU policies in agricultural trade and sustainable development is complex and encompasses a range of legal frameworks, strategies, and initiatives. While the EU has made significant strides in promoting sustainability through its agricultural and trade policies, achieving policy coherence remains challenging. A more integrated and holistic approach to policy-making, stronger enforcement mechanisms, enhanced stakeholder engagement, and targeted support for small-scale producers and developing countries will be essential for realizing the EU's vision of sustainable agricultural trade that aligns with the SDGs and global environmental agreements.

2.3. Analysis of Existing Legal Instruments and Their Impact on Policy Coherence

Existing EU legal instruments, such as the CAP, SPS agreements, and voluntary sustainability standards (e.g., Fair Trade and organic certifications), significantly impact trade dynamics and sustainability. However, challenges remain in aligning these instruments coherently with broader sustainability goals and addressing environmental protection, social equity, and fair trade gaps.

The EU's existing legal instruments, such as regulations, directives, and trade agreements, significantly impact policy coherence by defining the rules and standards that govern trade, environmental protection, and social development. For instance, the General Food Law (Regulation EC No 178/2002) establishes the principles and requirements of food law within the EU. It impacts agricultural products' production, processing, and trading (D4.1 Synthesis of Findings, 8). The General Food Law supports sustainable trade practices that align with EU sustainability goals and international standards by ensuring food safety and traceability.

However, the effectiveness of these legal instruments in promoting policy coherence is often limited by gaps in their design and implementation. For instance, while the CAP provides substantial subsidies to EU farmers to encourage sustainable practices, it has been criticised for failing to adequately support smallholder farmers in developing countries who face high compliance costs related to EU standards. Addressing these gaps requires more inclusive and flexible approaches to policy formulation that consider partner countries' diverse capacities and needs.

Moreover, the EU's trade agreements, such as the EPAs, have a mixed impact on policy coherence. While these agreements aim to enhance trade relationships and development cooperation, they often impose stringent environmental and social standards requirements that can be challenging for partner countries to meet. This can lead to unintended consequences, such as excluding small-scale producers from the benefits of trade liberalisation (Carbone, 2008, 330). Therefore, there is a need to enhance the coherence of these agreements by providing greater support for capacity building and compliance in partner countries (D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 9).

The EU's efforts to align its trade policies with global environmental agreements, such as the Paris Agreement and the Convention on Biological Diversity, are critical for ensuring policy coherence. The EU's regulatory frameworks, such as the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) and the Renewable Energy Directive (RED), are designed to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and promote renewable energy. However, aligning these frameworks with trade policies requires careful consideration of potential trade-offs, such as the impact of carbon pricing on competitiveness and the need to avoid creating new barriers to trade (European Commission, 2019; Meadowcroft, 2007).

The role of voluntary sustainability standards and certifications in promoting policy coherence cannot be underestimated. These standards, such as Fair Trade, Organic, and Rainforest Alliance, provide market-based incentives for producers to adopt sustainable practices. While they contribute to enhancing market access for sustainably produced goods, their effectiveness depends on the level of integration with national and international legal frameworks and the support provided for

compliance. Ensuring that these standards are aligned with broader policy objectives and do not become trade barriers is essential for achieving policy coherence (Mayer & Gereffi, 2017, 11).

Additionally, legal intellectual property rights (IPR) and innovation gaps must be addressed to promote policy coherence in trade and sustainability. For instance, the limited attention given to IPR in agricultural trade frameworks, particularly concerning patents, trademarks, and geographical indications, poses challenges to promoting innovation and fair competition (D4.1 Synthesis of Findings, 2). Strengthening IPR frameworks in the context of sustainable trade can help support innovation, protect traditional knowledge, and enhance the competitiveness of sustainable products in global markets.

The EU's legal instruments must also address social dimensions, such as labour and human rights, to ensure policy coherence. While some EU trade agreements include labour and human rights provisions, these provisions are often limited in scope and lack robust enforcement mechanisms. Strengthening these provisions and ensuring they are consistently applied across all trade agreements is crucial for promoting fair and equitable trade practices that align with SDGs and global development goals (D4.4 Report Webinar' Policy Coherence).

Finally, improving policy coordination and implementation mechanisms is essential for enhancing the coherence of the EU's legal and institutional frameworks. This includes creating cross-sectoral platforms for dialogue and collaboration among EU institutions, member states, and international partners. Such mechanisms can help address the complexities and trade-offs in aligning trade, environmental, and development policies and ensure that policy implementation supports sustainable development objectives (Nilsson et al., 2012).

The existing legal instruments governing the EU's agricultural trade, environmental protection, and development cooperation play a crucial role in shaping policy coherence for sustainable development. One of the primary legal instruments in this regard is the **Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)**, which has historically been a cornerstone of EU agricultural policy. The CAP provides substantial subsidies to EU farmers to encourage sustainable agricultural practices, support rural development, and ensure food security. However, despite recent reforms to better align the CAP with environmental and sustainability objectives, it faces criticism for providing subsidies that may inadvertently encourage intensive agricultural practices. These practices often result in increased greenhouse gas emissions, soil degradation, and biodiversity loss, contradicting the EU's broader environmental and climate goals under the European Green Deal and the Paris Agreement (European Commission, 2019; D4.1 Synthesis of Findings, 8-9).

The **General Food Law (Regulation EC No 178/2002)** is another critical legal framework that establishes the principles and requirements of food law within the EU, ensuring food safety and protecting consumer health. The law mandates strict standards for traceability, hygiene, and food safety, essential for maintaining high-quality agricultural imports and exports. However, the rigorous standards set by the General Food Law can pose challenges for small-scale producers in developing countries, who often lack the resources and technical capacity to comply. This creates a policy incoherence where stringent regulations intended to ensure food safety and quality may inadvertently limit market access for vulnerable producers, contradicting the EU's development cooperation objectives (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 9-10).

In addition to the CAP and the General Food Law, the **Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Directive (Directive 2011/92/EU)** and the **Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) Directive (Directive 2001/42/EC)** are critical legal instruments that play a vital role in integrating environmental considerations into EU policies and programs. These directives require assessing and considering environmental impacts in decision-making processes, particularly for large-scale agricultural projects and infrastructure development. While these directives provide essential safeguards for environmental protection, their application can vary significantly across member states, leading to inconsistencies in managing environmental impacts. This variation creates gaps in policy coherence, especially when environmental objectives clash with economic or trade priorities (European Commission, 2020; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 11-12).

The **EU Emissions Trading System (ETS)**, established under the EU's climate policy framework, is another significant legal instrument to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by limiting emissions from high-emitting sectors, including agriculture. While the ETS provides a market-based mechanism for reducing emissions, its application in the agricultural sector has been limited. Many argue that the ETS does not adequately address emissions from agricultural practices, such as methane emissions from livestock or nitrous oxide from fertilizers, creating a gap in the EU's climate policy that affects policy coherence with sustainability goals (Meadowcroft, 2007, 301; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 12-13).

Another legal instrument that impacts policy coherence is the **Renewable Energy Directive (Directive 2018/2001/EU)**, which promotes using renewable energy sources, including biofuels, in the EU. While this directive aims to reduce the EU's dependence on fossil fuels and promote energy sustainability, it has raised concerns about its impact on agricultural trade and sustainability. The production of biofuels can lead to competition for land and resources, resulting in deforestation, biodiversity loss, and food insecurity, particularly in developing countries that export agricultural products to the EU. This highlights a critical policy incoherence between the EU's

energy and environmental goals and its development cooperation objectives (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 10).

The **Sanitary and Phytosanitary (SPS) Measures** and **Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) Agreements** under the World Trade Organization (WTO) framework are also critical to understanding policy coherence. The EU applies these agreements to protect human, animal, and plant health and safety by setting standards for agricultural imports. However, the strict implementation of these measures can create significant barriers for agricultural exporters in developing countries, especially those lacking the capacity to meet EU standards. While these agreements are essential for ensuring food safety, their uneven application and impact can undermine the EU's efforts to promote fair and equitable trade relationships with developing countries (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, p. 13-14; Young & Peterson, 2013).

The **Economic Partnership Agreements (EPAs)** between the EU and African, Caribbean, and Pacific (ACP) countries provide another example of legal instruments with mixed impacts on policy coherence. While the EPAs aim to promote trade liberalization and development cooperation, they often impose stringent environmental and social standards requirements that can be challenging for ACP countries to meet. This has led to concerns that the EPAs, rather than fostering development, may exacerbate existing inequalities and create barriers for small-scale producers in these regions. Revising these agreements to include more flexible and supportive provisions for capacity building and compliance is essential for enhancing policy coherence and promoting sustainable development (Carbone, 2008, 331; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 14-15).

The **EU's Green Public Procurement (GPP) Policy** is another instrument that influences policy coherence, particularly in promoting sustainable agricultural practices. The GPP encourages public authorities to procure goods and services that meet high environmental standards, including sustainable agricultural products. However, while the GPP has the potential to drive demand for sustainable products and incentivize green practices, its uptake remains limited across member states. Moreover, the lack of uniform criteria and implementation guidelines has resulted in inconsistent application, reducing the policy's overall impact on promoting sustainable agricultural trade (European Commission, 2019; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, p. 15-16).

Moreover, the **EU's Trade and Sustainable Development (TSD) Chapters** within its free trade agreements (FTAs) are crucial to integrating environmental and labour standards into trade policies. However, their effectiveness has been questioned due to the lack of binding commitments and enforceable dispute-resolution mechanisms. Unlike other trade-related provisions subject to sanctions and penalties, TSD chapters often rely on dialogue and cooperation, which can be insufficient in cases of non-compliance. Strengthening the enforcement mechanisms within these chapters is

necessary to ensure that trade agreements effectively promote sustainable development (Mayer & Gereffi, 2017; Collste et al, 2017).

Finally, the **EU's External Investment Plan (EIP)**, which aims to promote sustainable development and inclusive growth in partner countries, particularly in Africa and the EU Neighborhood, also has implications for policy coherence. While the EIP seeks to mobilize private investment in sustainable projects, including the agricultural sector, ensuring that these investments align with local environmental, social, and development priorities is necessary. Without adequate safeguards, there is a risk that investment flows could contribute to unsustainable practices, such as land grabbing or environmental degradation, contradicting the EU's broader sustainability goals (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, p. 17).

By analyzing these existing legal instruments and their impact on policy coherence, it becomes clear that substantial gaps and inconsistencies remain while the EU has made significant efforts to integrate sustainability considerations into its legal frameworks. Addressing these gaps will require more integrated and holistic approaches to policy formulation and implementation, ensuring that trade, environmental, and development objectives are aligned and mutually reinforcing. Strengthening enforcement mechanisms, enhancing capacity-building support, and fostering greater coherence between legal instruments are essential to achieving sustainable agricultural trade and development goals.

3. Findings from Case Studies and Reports

3.1. Overview of Key Findings from the MATS Project Case Studies

The case studies comprehensively evaluate how legal and institutional frameworks impact sustainable agricultural practices and trade between the EU and partner countries. For the most part, they highlight the importance of compliance with EU regulations on food safety, environmental standards, and voluntary sustainability standards for market access and trade relationships (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 3-5).

The project's 15 case studies span diverse regions and agricultural sectors, focusing on sustainable agricultural trade's legal, regulatory, and institutional dimensions. These case studies reveal significant variations in how institutional frameworks impact agricultural practices, trade dynamics, and sustainability goals. They emphasise aligning trade policies with environmental and social sustainability objectives to achieve policy coherence (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 3-4).

Amongst the central findings from the case studies is the role of institutional frameworks in facilitating or hindering market access to the EU. For example, case studies from Tanzania, Uganda, and Ethiopia illustrate how compliance with EU regulations on food safety, quality standards, and sustainability certifications directly impacts their ability to access European markets. While compliance with such standards enhances the competitiveness of agricultural exports, it also presents challenges for small-scale producers, particularly in developing countries, who face high costs and technical barriers in meeting these requirements (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 4-5).

The case studies also highlight the role of domestic laws and policies in shaping trade dynamics with the EU. For instance, Finland's agricultural policies emphasise sustainability and environmental protection, aligning well with EU regulations and facilitating trade within the EU market. In contrast, countries like Tanzania and Uganda face challenges due to gaps in their legal and institutional frameworks, which hinder their ability to comply with EU standards fully. These gaps often relate to inadequate infrastructure, limited access to technology, and insufficient capacity for monitoring and enforcement (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 6-7).

Another important finding is the varying impact of international agreements on trade practices. For instance, the World Trade Organization (WTO) agreements on Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures (SPS) and Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) are critical

for ensuring that agricultural exports meet international safety and quality standards. However, their implementation varies significantly across regions and sectors, affecting trade dynamics and policy coherence. The case studies underscore the need for better alignment of domestic regulations with international standards to facilitate smoother trade flows and enhance policy coherence (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 8-9).

3.2. Synthesis of the Impact of Institutional Frameworks on Trade Dynamics with the EU

Institutional frameworks such as the EU's food safety and environmental regulations have a decisive impact in shaping agricultural trade dynamics between the EU and its partners. The various EU legal and institutional frameworks are aimed at ensuring that agricultural exports meet a number of health, safety, and sustainability standards, while also attempting to facilitate smoother transactions and reducing trade barriers (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 4-5).

The case studies collectively show that these institutional frameworks significantly influence trade dynamics between the EU and its partner countries. Undoubtedly, a well-structured institutional framework facilitates trade by reducing transaction costs, enhancing market access, and ensuring compliance with EU regulations. Conversely, the existence of gaps or inconsistencies in these frameworks leads to trade barriers, unequal market access, and missed opportunities for sustainable development (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 7-8).

One critical aspect highlighted by the case studies is the role of EU regulations in shaping trade dynamics. The EU's stringent food safety and environmental standards, such as the General Food Law (Regulation EC No 178/2002) and the EU's Farm to Fork Strategy, have significant implications for partner countries' agricultural exports. For instance, the requirement for traceability and adherence to maximum residue levels of pesticides creates a competitive advantage for those countries that can comply. However, it presents significant challenges for those who cannot (European Commission, 2020). It is clear, therefore, that compliance with these standards is essential for accessing the EU market but requires substantial investment in infrastructure, technology, and capacity building (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 9-10).

The case studies also highlight the importance of preferential trade agreements, such as the Everything But Arms (EBA) initiative and the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA), in enhancing trade dynamics with the EU. These agreements provide tariff-free access to the EU market for Least Developed Countries (LDCs) and promote intra-African trade, contributing to economic growth and development. However, the benefits of these agreements are often unevenly distributed, with small-scale

producers and marginalised groups facing significant challenges in accessing these opportunities due to high compliance costs and limited capacity for meeting EU standards (see D4.4 *Report Webinar' Policy Coherence*).

Furthermore, the institutional frameworks governing agricultural trade must be aligned with international environmental and climate agreements to enhance trade dynamics and policy coherence. The case studies reveal that compliance with agreements such as the Paris Agreement and the Convention on Biological Diversity is essential for maintaining access to environmentally conscious markets like the EU. For instance, Tanzania's compliance with the Kyoto Protocol and Uganda's adherence to the Convention on Biological Diversity enhance their sustainability credentials, making their agricultural exports more attractive to the EU market (D4.1 Synthesis of Findings, 5-6).

3.3. Challenges and Opportunities Identified in Current Frameworks

Challenges in current frameworks include high compliance costs for small-scale producers, inadequate attention to intellectual property rights, and insufficient support for marginalised groups. Opportunities lie in enhancing policy coherence, streamlining regulations, and fostering international cooperation (D4.4 *Report Webinar' Policy Coherence*).

Analysing institutional frameworks across the MATS project case studies reveals several challenges and opportunities for enhancing policy coherence and sustainable trade dynamics. One of the most significant challenges is the high cost of compliance with EU regulations on food safety, environmental standards, and sustainability certifications. These costs are often prohibitive for small-scale producers and marginalised groups in developing countries, leading to unequal access to trade opportunities and reinforcing existing inequalities (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 7-8).

Another challenge is the lack of coherence and integration between policy areas, such as trade, environment, and development cooperation. For example, while the EU's trade policies promote sustainability by including environmental and social standards, there is often a disconnect between these policies and development cooperation objectives. This incoherence can result in conflicting policy outcomes, where trade policies undermine development goals or vice versa (Carbone, 2008, 326). The case studies highlight the need for more integrated and coordinated policy approaches that align trade, environmental, and development objectives to enhance policy coherence and achieve sustainable development (D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 10-11).

The case studies also identified a significant challenge in the limited capacity for monitoring and enforcing legal and regulatory frameworks in partner countries. For instance, while countries like Ghana and Ethiopia have established environmental protection laws and regulations, their capacity to monitor and enforce these laws is often constrained by limited financial and technical resources. This lack of capacity undermines these frameworks' effectiveness and limits these countries' ability to comply with EU standards (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 6-7; Nilsson et al., 2012, 322).

Despite these challenges, the case studies also identify several opportunities for enhancing policy coherence and promoting sustainable trade. One such opportunity is leveraging voluntary sustainability standards and certifications, such as Fair Trade, Organic, and Rainforest Alliance, to enhance market access and promote sustainable agricultural practices. These standards provide market-based incentives for compliance, enhance access to environmentally and socially conscious markets, and contribute to sustainable development objectives. However, their effectiveness depends on the level of integration with national and international legal frameworks and the support provided for compliance (Mayer & Gereffi, 2017, 12; D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 8).

The analysis of current EU frameworks related to agricultural trade and sustainability reveals several challenges that undermine policy coherence and the ability to achieve the SDGs. One of the most prominent challenges is the *high compliance costs* associated with meeting EU standards on food safety, environmental sustainability, and labour rights. These costs are particularly burdensome for small-scale producers and cooperatives in developing countries, who often lack the financial resources, technical expertise, and infrastructure needed to comply with stringent EU regulations. This creates a significant barrier to market access, limiting the participation of smallholders in global agricultural trade and exacerbating existing inequalities (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 7-8; Carbone, 2008).

Another key challenge is the *lack of coherence and integration* between trade, environmental, and development policies within the EU. While the EU has tried to integrate sustainability considerations into its trade agreements, gaps remain in aligning these agreements with broader environmental and development objectives. For example, certain trade agreements may promote market liberalization and economic growth but fail to adequately address the environmental impacts of increased agricultural production, such as deforestation, soil degradation, and biodiversity loss. This policy fragmentation leads to conflicting outcomes and reduces the overall effectiveness of EU efforts to promote sustainable development (D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 10-11).

The *complexity of multi-level governance* within the EU also poses a significant challenge to policy coherence. Different levels of governance—EU institutions, member states, regional authorities, and local governments—often have varying priorities, capacities, and policy objectives. This can lead to inconsistencies in the implementation of EU policies and difficulties in coordinating actions across different governance levels. For example, while some member states have adopted ambitious sustainability targets and policies, others may lag in implementation due to political, economic, or social constraints. This uneven progress creates challenges for achieving a harmonized and coherent approach to sustainable agricultural trade across the EU (European Commission, 2020; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, p. 16-17).

The *insufficient enforcement of sustainability and human rights provisions* within trade agreements is another significant challenge. Many EU trade agreements include chapters on sustainable development and human rights, but these provisions often lack binding commitments and effective enforcement mechanisms. As a result, compliance with these provisions is often voluntary or weakly monitored, limiting their impact on the ground. Without more robust enforcement mechanisms, there is a risk that these provisions will remain symbolic rather than substantive, undermining the EU's credibility as a promoter of sustainable trade and human rights (Young & Peterson, 2013; Collste et al., 2017, 925).

Despite these challenges, there are also several opportunities for enhancing policy coherence and promoting sustainable agricultural trade. One significant opportunity lies in *leveraging digital technologies and innovations* to facilitate compliance with EU standards and enhance sustainability outcomes. Digital tools such as blockchain, remote sensing, and artificial intelligence can help improve traceability, transparency, and efficiency in agricultural supply chains. For example, blockchain technology can be used to track the origin and journey of agricultural products, ensuring compliance with sustainability standards and reducing the risk of fraud. By investing in digital infrastructure and promoting the adoption of innovative technologies, the EU can support more sustainable and inclusive agricultural trade practices (Mayer & Gereffi, 2017, 14; D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 9).

Another opportunity is to enhance *regional and international cooperation* to address shared challenges and promote sustainable development. The EU can lead in fostering regional partnerships, such as the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA), which aims to promote intra-African trade and economic integration. The EU can help build more resilient and sustainable agricultural sectors in developing countries by supporting regional trade agreements prioritising sustainability and inclusivity. Additionally, the EU can work with international organizations, such as the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) and the World Trade Organization (WTO), to develop frameworks that promote fair and sustainable trade practices globally (Carbone, 2008).

There is also an opportunity to strengthen *multi-stakeholder engagement and participatory governance* in policy development and implementation. Engaging a diverse range of stakeholders—including civil society organizations, private sector actors, academia, and local communities—in the policy process can help ensure that policies are more inclusive, transparent, and responsive to the needs of different groups. For example, the EU could establish multi-stakeholder platforms to facilitate dialogue, knowledge exchange, and collaboration on crucial agricultural trade and sustainability issues. These platforms could help build consensus, identify potential policy incoherencies, and develop innovative solutions to complex challenges (OECD, 2016).

Integrating *climate adaptation and resilience measures* into trade policies also presents a significant opportunity for enhancing policy coherence. While much of the focus has been on mitigation efforts, there is a growing recognition of the need to support climate adaptation in agricultural trade policies. This could incorporate provisions promoting climate-resilient agricultural practices, such as sustainable water management, agroforestry, and soil conservation, into trade agreements. By supporting climate adaptation measures, the EU can help build resilience in agricultural sectors, particularly in vulnerable regions, and reduce the risks associated with climate change (Meadowcroft, 2007; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 18).

Moreover, the EU has the opportunity to promote *inclusive value chains* that empower small-scale producers, women, and marginalized groups. This could involve developing targeted initiatives that provide access to finance, training, and capacity-building programs to help these groups participate more fully in global value chains. For instance, the EU could support women-led agricultural enterprises by providing grants, loans, and technical assistance to help them scale up and access international markets. By promoting inclusive value chains, the EU can contribute to poverty reduction, gender equality, and social inclusion, aligning with its broader development goals (Young & Peterson, 2013; D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 10).

Lastly, the EU could capitalize on the growing *consumer demand for sustainably produced and ethically sourced products* as an opportunity to drive sustainable agricultural trade. European consumers increasingly seek products that meet high environmental, social, and ethical standards, creating a market incentive for producers to adopt sustainable practices. The EU can support this trend by developing market mechanisms, such as green labelling and certification schemes, that help consumers make informed choices and encourage producers to comply with sustainability standards. This approach would create a virtuous cycle, where sustainable production is rewarded by market demand, further incentivizing sustainable practices (Mayer & Gereffi, 2017; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 13).

By addressing the identified challenges and seizing these opportunities, the EU can enhance the coherence of its agricultural trade policies with sustainable development objectives. This will require a concerted effort to integrate environmental, social, and economic dimensions into trade agreements, strengthen enforcement mechanisms, promote innovation and digitalization, foster multi-stakeholder engagement, support climate adaptation, and leverage consumer demand for sustainability. Through these actions, the EU can help build a more sustainable, inclusive, and resilient global trading system that aligns with the SDGs and its commitments under international environmental and climate agreements.

3.4. Specific Findings on Key Areas

Environmental Standards and Climate Action

Several case studies emphasise the need for coherent policies that align agricultural practices with climate action goals, such as the Paris Agreement (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 5-6).

The MATS project case studies emphasise the need for coherent policies that align agricultural practices with climate action goals, such as the Paris Agreement. For instance, the case study on Finnish dairy production illustrates how adherence to EU climate action policies, such as the Emissions Trading System (ETS) and the Effort Sharing Regulation, drives efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in agriculture. However, aligning these frameworks with trade policies requires careful consideration of potential trade-offs, such as the impact of carbon pricing on competitiveness and the need to avoid creating new barriers to trade (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 10-11; European Commission, 2019).

Intellectual Property Rights and Trade

Limited attention has been paid to intellectual property rights in agricultural trade, highlighting the need for greater focus on innovation and fair competition (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, p. 2).

The case studies highlight the limited attention to intellectual property rights (IPR) in agricultural trade. For instance, there is minimal coverage of IP laws related to agricultural innovations and plant varieties, which are crucial for promoting innovation and ensuring fair competition. Strengthening IPR frameworks in the context of sustainable trade can help support innovation, protect traditional knowledge, and enhance the competitiveness of sustainable products in global markets (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 2).

Labour and Human Rights

Regulatory frameworks often overlook labour and human rights, particularly in developing countries, which impacts equitable trade practices.

The case studies reveal that regulatory frameworks overlook labour and human rights, particularly in developing countries. For example, while some EU trade agreements include labour and human rights provisions, these provisions are often limited in scope and lack robust enforcement mechanisms. Strengthening these provisions and ensuring consistent application across all trade agreements is crucial for promoting fair and equitable trade practices that align with SDGs and global development goals (D4.4 *Report Webinar' Policy Coherence*).

Sustainable Agricultural Practices and Trade Policies

Integrating sustainability standards in trade policies is crucial for promoting responsible consumption and production in line with SDG 12 (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 8).

Integrating sustainability standards in trade policies is crucial for promoting responsible consumption and production in line with SDG 12. The case studies emphasise the role of sustainable agricultural practices in enhancing market access and trade relationships with the EU. For instance, the case study on the oats value chain in the Nordics highlights how compliance with EU sustainability standards, such as those outlined in the General Food Law Regulation and the Organic Production Regulation, ensures that oats from Finland and Sweden meet high-quality standards, facilitating trade within the EU (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 17; European Commission *Farm to Fork*, 2020).

Policy Gaps and Incoherencies

Finally, the case studies identify several areas where the legal and regulatory frameworks are lacking or insufficiently addressed. These include intellectual property rights, gender equality, comprehensive human rights, and labour protections. Addressing these gaps ensures a more inclusive, sustainable, and competitive agricultural sector. The case studies underscore the need for continuous capacity building, technological investment, and international cooperation to help these producers meet the required standards and fully benefit from trade opportunities with the EU (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 15-16).

4. Analysis of Gaps and Incoherencies in Current Frameworks

4.1. Identified Policy Incoherencies and Gaps

The analysis reveals significant gaps and incoherencies in current EU frameworks, particularly in aligning trade policies with environmental and social sustainability goals. These gaps affect partner countries' ability to meet EU standards and participate in equitable trade relationships (D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 10-12).

The analysis of current EU frameworks related to agricultural trade, sustainability, and development cooperation reveals several policy incoherencies and gaps that undermine efforts to achieve sustainable development. One of the most significant incoherencies is the disconnect between trade policies and environmental objectives. For example, while the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) includes provisions to promote sustainable farming practices and reduce environmental impacts, it also provides subsidies that sometimes incentivise intensive agricultural practices. These subsidies can lead to increased greenhouse gas emissions, deforestation, and biodiversity loss, contradicting the EU's broader environmental goals under the European Green Deal and the Paris Agreement (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 6-7; European Commission, 2019).

Another critical gap is the lack of integration between trade and development policies. While the EU has made strides in incorporating sustainability standards into trade agreements, such as the Economic Partnership Agreements (EPAs), these agreements often fail to address partner countries' development needs adequately. For instance, stringent sanitary and phytosanitary (SPS) measures and technical trade barriers (TBT) can exclude small-scale producers in developing countries who cannot meet these standards. This creates a policy incoherence where trade policies intended to promote development reinforce inequalities and limit market access for vulnerable groups (Carbone, 2008, 330; D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 6-7).

Another critical gap is the absence of robust enforcement mechanisms for sustainability and human rights standards within trade agreements. Many EU trade agreements include chapters on sustainable development, but these provisions often lack binding commitments or effective enforcement mechanisms. As a result, compliance with labour, environmental, and human rights standards is often

voluntary or poorly monitored, leading to limited impact on the ground (Young & Peterson, 2013, 505). This gap undermines the EU's ability to promote fair and sustainable trade practices that align with the.

There is also a significant policy incoherence related to intellectual property rights (IPR) and innovation in agricultural trade. The case studies reveal that IPR frameworks, particularly those concerning patents, trademarks, and geographical indications, receive minimal attention in the context of sustainable trade. This lack of focus on IPR can hinder innovation, restrict access to traditional knowledge, and limit the development of sustainable agricultural practices. Strengthening IPR frameworks to support innovation and protect traditional knowledge is essential for enhancing policy coherence and promoting sustainable development (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 2).

The uneven application of environmental regulations across different sectors and regions further highlights gaps in policy coherence. For example, while the EU's Farm to Fork Strategy aims to reduce pesticide use and promote organic farming, its impact varies significantly across member states and sectors. Some regions have made substantial progress in reducing pesticide use and promoting sustainable farming, while others rely heavily on chemical inputs. This uneven implementation can create trade distortions and undermine the EU's efforts to achieve policy coherence in agricultural trade and sustainability (European Commission *Farm to Fork*, 2020; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 11-12).

4.2. Impact on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and Global Environmental Agreements

Current policy incoherencies hinder progress towards achieving SDGs, particularly those related to climate action (SDG 13), responsible consumption (SDG 12), and partnerships for the goals (SDG 17). Greater alignment with global environmental agreements is needed to enhance policy coherence (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 9-10).

The identified policy incoherencies and gaps in the current EU frameworks have significant implications for achieving the SDGs and global environmental agreements. For instance, the lack of coherence between trade and environmental policies directly affects SDG 13 (Climate Action). While the EU is committed to reducing its carbon footprint and promoting climate resilience, incoherent policies that support intensive agricultural practices can increase greenhouse gas emissions and contribute to climate change, undermining efforts to meet global climate targets (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 7-8; European Commission, 2019).

Similarly, gaps in integrating social and development objectives in trade agreements impact SDG 1 (No Poverty) and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities). EU trade policies that impose stringent standards without adequate compliance support can exacerbate poverty and inequality in developing countries. For example, small-scale farmers in Sub-Saharan Africa often struggle to meet the EU's SPS and TBT requirements, limiting their access to lucrative EU markets. This undermines poverty reduction efforts and contradicts the EU's commitment to promoting inclusive and sustainable development (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 9-10; Mayer & Gereffi, 2017).

The limited enforcement of labour and human rights standards within trade agreements also affects SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth). While EU trade agreements often include provisions on labour rights, the lack of binding commitments and effective monitoring mechanisms means these provisions are rarely enforced. This can lead to exploitative labour practices and poor working conditions in partner countries, undermining efforts to promote decent work and sustainable economic growth (Young & Peterson, 2013, 504; Picciotto, 2005).

The gaps in IPR frameworks and the limited focus on innovation in agricultural trade impact SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) and SDG 2 (Zero Hunger). More robust IPR frameworks that promote innovation and protect traditional knowledge can support the development of sustainable agricultural practices and enhance food security. However, the lack of focus on IPR within trade agreements limits the potential for innovation and development in the agricultural sector, hindering progress towards these goals (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 2).

Furthermore, the uneven implementation of environmental regulations across sectors and regions affects SDG 15 (Life on Land) and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production). While some regions have made progress in promoting sustainable agricultural practices, others continue to rely on unsustainable practices that contribute to deforestation, land degradation, and biodiversity loss. This uneven progress creates challenges for achieving policy coherence and meeting the EU's commitments under global environmental agreements such as the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (European Commission, 2020; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 12-13).

4.3. Regional and Sectoral Variations in the Application and Impact of Frameworks

There are notable regional and sectoral variations in how frameworks are applied and their impact on sustainable agricultural practices and trade dynamics. These differences must be addressed through more tailored and context-specific approaches (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 6-7).

The analysis of current frameworks reveals significant regional and sectoral variations in the application and impact of EU policies on agricultural trade and sustainability. These variations are often influenced by differences in economic development, institutional capacity, and environmental conditions across regions and sectors. For example, Northern European countries like Finland and Sweden have advanced regulatory frameworks and stronger institutional capacities to implement sustainability standards in agricultural trade. These countries have successfully aligned their agricultural practices with EU sustainability goals, enhancing their competitiveness in the EU market (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 16-17).

In contrast, many developing countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, such as Tanzania and Uganda, face significant challenges in aligning their agricultural practices with EU standards. These challenges are often related to limited access to technology, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient capacity for monitoring and enforcement. As a result, small-scale producers in these countries struggle to meet the EU's stringent food safety, environmental, and sustainability standards, limiting their access to EU markets and undermining their ability to benefit from trade liberalisation (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 11-12; Carbone, 2008).

Sectoral variations are also evident in the impact of EU frameworks on trade dynamics and sustainability. For example, the dairy sector in the Nordic countries has successfully adopted climate-resilient farming practices, aligning with the EU's climate action goals and enhancing market access. However, other sectors, such as horticulture in Sub-Saharan Africa, face greater challenges due to their reliance on chemical inputs and limited access to organic farming technologies. These sectoral differences highlight the need for more tailored and context-specific approaches to policy formulation and implementation to enhance policy coherence and promote sustainable trade (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 17).

The varying levels of policy coherence across regions and sectors also affect the EU's ability to meet its global environmental commitments. For instance, while the EU's Farm to Fork Strategy aims to promote sustainable food systems and reduce environmental impacts, its implementation has been uneven across member states and sectors. Some regions have made substantial progress in reducing pesticide use and promoting organic farming, while others continue to lag, creating trade distortions and undermining the EU's efforts to achieve policy coherence in agricultural trade and sustainability (European Commission *Farm to Fork*, 2020; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 14-15).

These regional and sectoral variations also reflect the differences in the capacity for policy coordination and implementation among EU member states and partner countries. In countries with strong institutional frameworks and high levels of policy

integration, such as Finland and Sweden, there is greater coherence between trade, environmental, and development policies. However, in countries with weaker institutional capacities, policy fragmentation and incoherence are more pronounced, creating challenges for achieving sustainable development goals and enhancing trade relationships with the EU (Nilsson et al., 2012, 321; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 19).

The uneven impact of EU trade policies on different regions and sectors also underscores the importance of capacity building and technical support for developing countries. The case studies highlight the need for more targeted support to help small-scale producers and marginalised groups in developing countries comply with EU standards and benefit from trade opportunities. This support could include financial assistance, technical training, and capacity-building programs that enhance compliance with sustainability standards and promote inclusive and equitable trade practices (D4.4 *Report Webinar' Policy Coherence*; Mayer & Gereffi, 2017, 12).

5. Recommendations for Enhancing EU Legal and Institutional Frameworks

5.1. Strengthening Policy Coherence with SDGs

This paper's recommendations include integrating SDG targets into all levels of EU policy-making and ensuring that trade policies support rather than undermine development objectives (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 12-13).

To enhance policy coherence with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the EU must integrate SDG targets more explicitly into its trade, environmental, and agricultural policies. This integration requires aligning all policy areas and considering the broader social, economic, and environmental impacts. One decisive recommendation could be to develop a *Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development (PCSD) Framework* that incorporates SDGs into all stages of the policy cycle – from formulation to implementation and monitoring (OECD, 2023).

The effective implementation of the PCSD framework can be achieved by establishing clear guidelines for policy alignment with SDGs and conducting regular impact assessments to evaluate policy coherence. The EU could institutionalise these impact assessments by integrating them into the policy development process, ensuring that all proposed policies are reviewed for their potential impacts on sustainable development objectives. This would involve setting up dedicated units within the European Commission and member states' governments responsible for conducting these assessments and reporting on the coherence of policies with SDGs (Carbone, 2008, 331; Nilsson et al., 2012, 320).

Additionally, the EU should strengthen its inter-institutional cooperation mechanisms to promote coherence across different policy domains. This could involve establishing an institution, such as a *Policy Coherence Observatory*, to track and monitor policy development across the European Commission, European Parliament, and European Council, with a goal to ensure alignment with the SDGs. Such an observatory could also provide platforms for stakeholders, including civil society, the private sector, and academia, to contribute to policy discussions and identify potential incoherencies early in policy formulation (generally, Young & Peterson, 2013).

5.2. Addressing Legal Gaps in Environmental and Climate Agreements

The EU needs to strengthen its commitment to international environmental and climate agreements by integrating more robust legal mechanisms to ensure compliance and accountability (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 14-15).

In this sense, the EU's legal frameworks must be strengthened to ensure that its trade policies align with global environmental and climate agreements, such as the Paris Agreement and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). The EU should revise existing trade agreements to address legal gaps, including more binding environmental protection and climate action commitments. This could involve adding legally enforceable clauses that require compliance with international environmental standards and provide mechanisms for dispute resolution in cases of non-compliance (European Commission *EU Green Deal*, 2019; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 14-15).

Furthermore, the EU should enhance its *Regulatory Impact Assessment (RIA)* procedures to evaluate trade policies' environmental and climate implications. These assessments should be mandatory for all new trade agreements and revisions to existing agreements. They could include specific indicators of greenhouse gas emissions, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable resource management. The results of these assessments should be publicly available, providing transparency and accountability and enabling stakeholders to hold policymakers accountable for incoherent policies (Meadowcroft, 2007, 305).

The EU could also promote greater alignment between its trade policies and global environmental commitments by developing *Green Trade Agreements* that prioritise sustainability objectives. These agreements could include specific provisions on carbon reduction, sustainable land use, and conservation and provide incentives for countries that demonstrate high levels of environmental performance. Such agreements would signal the EU's commitment to promoting sustainable trade and encourage other trading partners to adopt similar standards (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 15-16).

To effectively address the legal gaps in environmental and climate agreements, the EU must strengthen its existing trade and environmental policies by ensuring that they are better aligned with international environmental obligations, such as the Paris Agreement, the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). One critical recommendation is to enhance the *Environmental and Climate Clauses* in EU trade agreements to include binding commitments that are enforceable through legal mechanisms. This could involve revising current trade agreements to ensure that environmental and

climate commitments are not only declarative but also legally binding, with clear consequences for non-compliance (European Commission *EU Green Deal*, 2019; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 14-15).

A practical approach to implementing this recommendation is integrating *Environmental Dispute Settlement Mechanisms* within trade agreements that specifically address violations of environmental and climate commitments. These mechanisms could function similarly to existing dispute resolution procedures under the World Trade Organization (WTO) but with a focus on environmental and climate issues. They would allow for the timely resolution of disputes and provide a platform for affected parties, including civil society and non-governmental organizations, to hold parties accountable for breaches of environmental standards. Moreover, these mechanisms could incentivize compliance through sanctions or trade remedies, reinforcing the EU's commitment to sustainable trade practices (Meadowcroft, 2007, 302; Young & Peterson, 2013).

Additionally, the EU should consider establishing a framework for *Environmental Conditionality* in its trade agreements, making preferential access to the EU market contingent upon meeting specific environmental and climate criteria. Such a framework would require that partner countries demonstrate tangible progress toward meeting environmental targets, such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, preserving biodiversity, and promoting sustainable land use. The EU could support compliance through technical assistance, capacity-building programs, and financial incentives. This approach would align with the "carrot and stick" model, where positive reinforcement through rewards is balanced with punitive measures for non-compliance (OECD, 2023, 45).

To ensure the effectiveness of these measures, the EU must also enhance its *Regulatory Impact Assessment (RIA)* procedures to systematically evaluate the environmental implications of its trade policies. These assessments should be mandatory and comprehensive, covering all potential environmental impacts, such as emissions, deforestation, water use, and biodiversity loss. Furthermore, the RIA process should involve public consultations with key stakeholders, including environmental organizations, industry representatives, and affected communities, to ensure that diverse perspectives are considered in policy formulation. By making these assessments transparent and participatory, the EU can enhance accountability and build greater public trust in its environmental commitments (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 15-16; Mayer & Gereffi, 2017, 10).

Moreover, the EU should promote greater *Synergy between Multilateral Environmental Agreements (MEAs)* and its trade policies by incorporating the principles and obligations of MEAs into its legal frameworks. For example, provisions

related to the CBD could be embedded in EU trade agreements to ensure that trade practices do not undermine biodiversity goals. Similarly, the EU could integrate the principles of the UNFCCC into its trade policies to ensure that trade does not contribute to climate change. This would require a coordinated effort among EU institutions, member states, and international partners to harmonize environmental standards and ensure that trade policies mutually support global environmental objectives (D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 12-13; European Commission *Farm to Fork*, 2020).

Addressing these legal gaps and ensuring a more cohesive and enforceable approach to environmental and climate agreements, the EU can lead by example in promoting sustainable trade practices globally. Integrating robust legal mechanisms, environmental conditionality, and comprehensive regulatory assessments will strengthen the EU's ability to meet its environmental commitments and support a more sustainable and resilient global economy. These actions will also enhance the EU's credibility as a global leader in sustainability, encouraging other regions to adopt similar approaches to align trade and environmental objectives (Young & Peterson, 2013; OECD, 2016, 100).

To further strengthen the EU's ability to address legal gaps in environmental and climate agreements, it is crucial to integrate *Climate Resilience and Adaptation Measures* directly into trade agreements. While the EU has emphasized mitigation efforts, such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, there is a need to focus on climate adaptation strategies within trade policies. This could involve including provisions that require partner countries to implement climate adaptation plans, such as water management systems, sustainable land use practices, and infrastructure development that can withstand climate-related impacts. These adaptation measures would not only support the environmental integrity of trade relationships but also help build resilience in vulnerable economies, making them less susceptible to the adverse effects of climate change. Additionally, linking trade benefits, such as reduced tariffs or improved market access, to demonstrable progress in climate adaptation could further incentivize compliance (European Commission, 2019; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 16-17).

Moreover, the EU should develop a comprehensive *Monitoring and Compliance Framework* to meet environmental and climate commitments within trade agreements. This framework could establish an independent monitoring body responsible for assessing and verifying compliance with environmental provisions, similar to how the WTO monitors trade practices. This body could conduct regular audits, field visits, and assessments, providing transparent and evidence-based compliance evaluations. It could also include a system of reporting that requires partner countries to submit regular updates on their progress toward meeting

environmental targets, which a panel of experts could then review. If non-compliance is detected, the framework could provide a graduated response mechanism, starting with technical assistance and capacity-building support and escalating to more stringent measures, such as financial penalties or trade restrictions (Mayer & Gereffi, 2017; OECD, 2016, 105-106).

Lastly, the EU should prioritize creating *Inclusive Environmental Governance Mechanisms* that actively involve stakeholders from both the EU and partner countries, including local communities, civil society organizations, indigenous groups, and the private sector. This would ensure that trade agreements and environmental policies are developed and implemented in a participatory and transparent manner. For instance, the EU could establish joint environmental committees within each trade agreement to provide a forum for dialogue, review progress, and address concerns related to environmental compliance. These committees could play a crucial role in building trust, facilitating knowledge exchange, and ensuring that trade policies are responsive to the needs and priorities of all stakeholders. Such mechanisms would enhance the legitimacy and fairness of EU trade policies and strengthen their effectiveness in promoting sustainable development and environmental protection (Young & Peterson, 2013, 509).

By incorporating these detailed measures—focusing on climate resilience and adaptation, establishing robust monitoring and compliance frameworks, and fostering inclusive governance—the EU can significantly close the legal gaps in its environmental and climate agreements. This holistic approach would reinforce the EU's position as a global leader in sustainable trade and environmental stewardship, ensuring its trade policies align with international environmental commitments and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

5.3. Improving Mechanisms for Policy Coordination and Implementation

Better coordination among EU institutions, member states, and international partners is crucial for enhancing policy coherence. This includes creating cross-sectoral platforms for dialogue and collaboration (*D4.4 Report Webinar' Policy Coherence*).

Policy coordination and implementation are critical for achieving policy coherence across the EU's diverse policy landscape. One recommendation is to establish *Integrated Policy Coordination Mechanisms* that bring together representatives from different policy domains, such as trade, environment, development cooperation, and agriculture. These mechanisms would facilitate dialogue and coordination among policymakers, ensuring that policies are developed more effectively and potential incoherencies are identified and addressed early in the policy process.

To enhance policy coordination, the EU could introduce a *Coherence Scorecard* system that evaluates the degree of alignment between different policy areas and sustainable development objectives. This scorecard could be used by the European Commission, member states, and other EU institutions to assess the coherence of their policies and make necessary adjustments. The scorecard could also be a tool for benchmarking and sharing best practices among member states, encouraging continuous improvement in policy coherence (Mayer & Gereffi, 2017, 9; OECD, 2023, 50).

Moreover, the EU should invest in *Capacity-Building Programs* for policymakers at all levels to strengthen their understanding of policy coherence and the SDGs. These programs could include training sessions, workshops, and exchange programs that promote knowledge-sharing and collaboration among policymakers, civil society organisations, and the private sector. By building capacity and fostering a culture of policy coherence, the EU can ensure that its policies are more effectively coordinated and aligned with sustainable development objectives (Nilsson et al., 2012, 322; Young & Peterson, 2013, 502).

To effectively enhance policy coherence across various domains—such as trade, environment, agriculture, and development—the EU must prioritize the development of robust and integrated *Policy Coordination Frameworks* that facilitate cross-sectoral collaboration. One approach is establishing a centralized *Policy Coherence Coordination Unit* within the European Commission that is a focal point for integrating sustainable development objectives across different policy areas. This unit would coordinate policy development processes, ensure that all proposed policies undergo a rigorous coherence check against SDGs, and identify potential conflicts early in the policy formulation (OECD, 2023, 45; Young & Peterson, 2013, 509-10).

To operationalize this coordination unit, the EU could develop a *Coherence Review Mechanism* that involves representatives from key directorates-general (DGs), such as DG Trade, DG Environment, DG Agriculture and Rural Development, and DG International Partnerships. This mechanism would serve as a platform for regular inter-departmental consultations to review new policy proposals and amendments, assess their coherence with existing policies and SDGs and recommend adjustments. Such a mechanism could also include a mandatory *Coherence Impact Statement* for each new policy, detailing its potential effects on sustainability, trade, and development objectives (Meadowcroft, 2007, 308-309; Nilsson et al., 2012).

Another recommendation is establishing a *European Policy Coherence Task Force* that brings together policymakers, researchers, civil society, and private sector stakeholders to address specific policy incoherencies. This task force could function as a think tank, providing evidence-based analysis, strategic recommendations, and

innovative solutions for enhancing policy coordination and coherence. It would focus on complex issues that require cross-sectoral collaboration, such as aligning trade policies with climate goals or integrating environmental standards into agricultural practices. The task force could also serve as a forum for knowledge exchange, facilitating the sharing of best practices and lessons learned from different sectors and member states (Carbone, 2008, 331; OECD, 2023. 47).

The EU should also consider adopting a Clustered Policy Approach that groups related policy areas under thematic clusters to enhance horizontal policy coordination. For example, sustainable agriculture, food systems, and rural development policies could be grouped under an "Agriculture and Sustainability" cluster. This clustering would facilitate more integrated policy development and implementation, enabling policymakers to address cross-cutting issues more effectively. It would also help reduce siloed approaches within different DGs and promote a more holistic view of sustainable development challenges.

To further strengthen vertical policy coordination between the EU, member states, and local governments, the EU could implement a *Multi-Level Governance Framework* that aligns policy objectives and implementation strategies across different levels of governance. This framework would involve establishing joint policy development committees that include representatives from the EU institutions, national governments, regional authorities, and municipalities. These committees would ensure that policies are tailored to different regions' specific needs and contexts and that local governments have the necessary resources and capacities to implement them effectively. The framework would also facilitate better alignment of national and local policies with EU-level objectives, thereby enhancing overall policy coherence (European Commission, 2020; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 11-12).

To address implementation challenges, the EU should invest in developing *Digital Policy Coordination Tools* that facilitate real-time data sharing, monitoring, and coordination among different institutions and stakeholders. These tools could include online platforms and databases that provide up-to-date information on policy developments, impact assessments, and progress toward achieving SDG targets. By leveraging digital technologies, the EU can enhance transparency, accountability, and responsiveness in policy coordination, allowing for more agile and adaptive policy responses to emerging challenges (Mayer & Gereffi, 2017; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 19).

Furthermore, the EU should enhance its capacity-building efforts to support effective policy coordination and implementation. This could involve developing *Policy Coherence Training Programs* for policymakers, civil servants, and stakeholders at all levels. These programs could cover critical topics such as the principles of policy

coherence for sustainable development, policy impact assessment tools, cross-sectoral collaboration strategies, and best practices for integrated policy-making. By building capacity and fostering a culture of policy coherence, the EU can strengthen the ability of its institutions and member states to develop and implement more coordinated and effective policies (Meadowcroft, 2007, 310; Nilsson et al., 2012, 322).

Finally, the EU could establish a *Policy Coherence Monitoring and Evaluation System* that provides regular assessments of the effectiveness of policy coordination mechanisms and their impact on achieving sustainable development objectives. This system could include a set of coherence indicators that measure the alignment of policies with SDGs and other global commitments. Regular monitoring and evaluation reports could be published to provide transparency and accountability, highlight areas for improvement, and encourage continuous learning and adaptation in policy development and implementation (OECD, 2016, 118; Young & Peterson, 2013).

By adopting these detailed measures—centralizing policy coordination, clustering related policies, enhancing multi-level governance, leveraging digital tools, building capacity, and establishing robust monitoring and evaluation systems—the EU can significantly improve its policy coordination and implementation mechanisms. This comprehensive approach would ensure that policies are more integrated, coherent, and aligned with sustainable development goals, strengthening the EU’s leadership in promoting global sustainability.

5.4. Promoting Fair Trade, Sustainability, and Inclusivity in EU and Global Agricultural Trade

Concrete steps include revising trade agreements to incorporate more explicit environmental and social standards provisions and providing greater support for capacity building and compliance in developing countries (D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 11-12).

The EU's trade policies should prioritise fairness, sustainability, and inclusivity to promote equitable trade relationships and sustainable development. One way to achieve this is by revising trade agreements to include more comprehensive *Sustainability Chapters* that cover environmental, social, and economic dimensions. These chapters should include binding commitments on sustainable agricultural practices, fair labour standards, and gender equality, with precise mechanisms for monitoring and enforcement (European Commission, 2020; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 11-12).

To promote inclusivity, the EU could introduce *Inclusive Trade Initiatives* that provide targeted support for small-scale producers, women, and marginalised groups in developing countries. These initiatives could include financial assistance, technical support, and capacity-building programs that help these groups comply with EU standards and benefit from trade opportunities. The EU could also work with international organisations, such as the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) and the International Labour Organization (ILO), to develop frameworks that promote fair and inclusive trade practices globally.

Additionally, the EU should strengthen its support for *Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS)*, such as Fair Trade, Organic, and Rainforest Alliance certifications, to promote sustainable agricultural practices and enhance market access for sustainably produced goods. This could involve providing financial incentives for producers who adopt VSS, facilitating access to certification programs, and supporting market development for sustainably produced products. By promoting the use of VSS, the EU can encourage more sustainable and inclusive agricultural trade practices that align with the SDGs (see Mayer & Gereffi, 2017; D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 8).

To promote fair trade, sustainability, and inclusivity in agricultural trade, the EU must strengthen the integration of environmental, social, and economic dimensions within its trade agreements. A fundamental step is to ensure that all EU trade agreements include comprehensive and binding *Sustainability Chapters* that address environmental protection, labour rights, gender equality, and social inclusion. These chapters should set high standards and include specific enforcement mechanisms to ensure compliance. By making sustainability obligations legally binding rather than voluntary, the EU can enhance the effectiveness of its trade agreements in promoting sustainable development goals (SDGs) and protecting the rights of marginalised communities (European Commission, 2020; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 11-12).

One effective way to implement these commitments is by creating a *Sustainability Scorecard* for all trade agreements. This scorecard would evaluate each partner country's compliance with the sustainability provisions outlined in the agreements, including metrics on environmental performance, social equity, and human rights. The scorecard would be updated annually and publicly available, increasing transparency and accountability. Countries that score well could be rewarded with enhanced trade benefits, such as reduced tariffs or improved market access. At the same time, those who fail to meet sustainability criteria could face penalties or have their trade benefits reduced. This approach would incentivise countries to adhere to sustainability standards (Meadowcroft, 2007, 312; Young & Peterson, 2013, 512).

Additionally, the EU should expand its support for *Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS)*, such as Fair Trade, Organic, Rainforest Alliance, and Global GAP certifications. VSS play a critical role in promoting sustainable agricultural practices by providing market-based incentives for producers to adopt environmentally friendly and socially responsible practices. However, the uptake of these standards is often limited by high certification costs, particularly for small-scale producers in developing countries. To address this, the EU could establish a *Sustainability Certification Fund* to subsidize the costs of obtaining and maintaining certifications for smallholders and cooperatives. This would lower entry barriers and enable more producers to access premium markets (Mayer & Gereffi, 2017, 8; D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 8).

The EU can also promote fair trade and inclusivity by developing *Inclusive Trade Policy Frameworks* that prioritize the needs of small-scale farmers, women, and marginalized groups. These frameworks could include specific measures to support their integration into global value chains, such as providing access to finance, training, and capacity-building programs. For example, targeted initiatives could focus on supporting women-led agricultural enterprises, promoting gender equity in trade, and ensuring women have equal access to resources, markets, and decision-making processes. Such an inclusive approach would enhance equity and fairness and contribute to broader development goals, such as poverty reduction and social inclusion (OECD, 2023, 40).

To further promote sustainability and inclusivity in trade, the EU should encourage the formation of *Fair Trade and Sustainable Development Coalitions* that bring together governments, civil society organisations, private sector actors, and international organisations to promote fair trade practices. These coalitions could serve as platforms for dialogue, knowledge exchange, and capacity building, focusing on responsible sourcing, sustainable supply chains, and fair pricing mechanisms. They could also help develop and disseminate best practices for sustainable and inclusive trade, facilitating the adoption of fair trade principles across different regions and sectors (Carbone, 2008; King et al., 2012).

Moreover, the EU could introduce *Sustainable Agricultural Trade Hubs* in key partner countries, providing technical support, training, and resources to local producers, cooperatives, and exporters. These hubs could serve as centres of excellence for sustainable agricultural practices, offering services such as soil testing, pest management advice, and guidance on sustainable farming techniques. By establishing such hubs, the EU can build local capacities, enhance compliance with EU standards, and foster more sustainable and inclusive agricultural trade practices (Meadowcroft, 2007; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 17).

Addressing Trade Imbalances and Asymmetries in EU trade agreements with developing countries is crucial to ensure fair and inclusive agricultural trade. This

involves revising existing trade agreements to remove tariff and non-tariff barriers disproportionately affecting small-scale producers in developing countries. For instance, the EU could negotiate more favourable terms for agricultural exports from Least Developed Countries (LDCs), such as granting duty-free and quota-free access for all agricultural products. This would provide small-scale producers a more level playing field and help reduce global trade inequalities (European Commission, 2020; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 12-13).

Another critical strategy is promoting agroecological and regenerative farming practices through trade policies that encourage sustainable agricultural development. The EU could include specific provisions in its trade agreements that promote agroecological practices, such as crop rotation, agroforestry, and integrated pest management, which enhance biodiversity, soil health, and climate resilience. Providing technical and financial support for adopting these practices would improve sustainability outcomes and help build resilience against climate change and market shocks (Mayer & Gereffi, 2017; D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 9).

Furthermore, the EU could develop a *Fair Trade Impact Assessment (FTIA)* tool to evaluate its trade agreements' social, economic, and environmental impacts on small-scale producers, women, and marginalized groups. This tool would involve conducting participatory assessments with affected communities, ensuring their voices are heard and their needs are considered in trade policy formulation. The results of these assessments could inform the design of more equitable trade agreements and policies, ensuring that trade benefits are more widely distributed and that negative impacts are minimized (OECD, 2023).

Finally, the EU should enhance *Stakeholder Engagement and Participatory Governance* in trade policy development and implementation. This could involve creating multi-stakeholder platforms at the EU and partner country levels to ensure that all voices, including those of small-scale farmers, indigenous peoples, women, and youth, are represented in trade negotiations and decision-making processes. Engaging diverse stakeholders would help build consensus, increase the legitimacy of trade agreements, and ensure that policies are more inclusive, responsive, and effective in promoting fair trade and sustainability (Young & Peterson, 2013; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 19).

By implementing these detailed measures—creating sustainability scorecards, supporting VSS, developing inclusive frameworks, establishing coalitions and hubs, addressing trade imbalances, promoting agroecological practices, conducting impact assessments, and enhancing stakeholder engagement—the EU can effectively promote fair, sustainable, and inclusive agricultural trade. These efforts will reinforce the EU's commitment to sustainable development and help build a more equitable and resilient global trading system that benefits all.

5.5. Enhancing Support for Capacity Building and Compliance in Developing Countries

The EU should increase financial and technical support for capacity building in developing countries to help them meet EU standards and participate fully in sustainable trade.

Capacity building is crucial for enabling developing countries to comply with EU standards and benefit from trade opportunities. The EU should enhance its support for *Capacity-Building and Technical Assistance Programs* that help developing countries strengthen their regulatory frameworks, improve infrastructure, and build the technical capacity needed to comply with EU standards. These programs could focus on food safety, environmental protection, and sustainable agricultural practices, providing targeted support to small-scale producers and marginalised groups; Nilsson et al., 2012).

To effectively implement capacity-building initiatives, the EU should adopt a *Partnership-Based Approach* that involves close collaboration with partner countries, international organisations, civil society, and the private sector. This approach would ensure that capacity-building programs are tailored to partner countries' specific needs and contexts and implemented to maximise impact and sustainability. The EU could also establish a *Capacity-Building Fund* to provide financial resources for these initiatives, with contributions from member states, the private sector, and development partners (Carbone, 2008, 333-334; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 17).

Furthermore, the EU should support the development of *Regional Capacity-Building Networks* that facilitate knowledge-sharing and collaboration among developing countries. These networks could focus on regions such as Sub-Saharan Africa or Southeast Asia and provide platforms for exchanging best practices, technical expertise, and policy innovations. By fostering regional cooperation, the EU can help developing countries build the capacity to comply with EU standards and benefit from sustainable trade opportunities (Meadowcroft, 2007; OECD, 2023, 42).

To enhance compliance with EU standards, the EU could also introduce *Compliance Facilitation Mechanisms* that provide technical assistance, financial support, and capacity-building for partner countries that face challenges in meeting EU requirements. These mechanisms could include tailored action plans that address specific compliance issues and provide support for implementing corrective measures. The EU could also establish *Compliance Partnerships* with key trading partners to facilitate dialogue, exchange best practices, and address compliance challenges collaboratively (European Commission *EU Green Deal*, 2019; D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 12-13).

Finally, the EU should invest in *Monitoring and Evaluation Systems* to assess the effectiveness of its capacity-building and compliance support programs. These systems should include policy coherence, sustainable development, trade performance indicators, and provide regular feedback on program outcomes. By continuously monitoring and evaluating these programs, the EU can identify areas for improvement, adjust its support strategies, and ensure that its capacity-building efforts are aligned with sustainable development objectives.

6. Conclusion

6.1. Summary of Key Points and Findings

This paper summarised the main findings from Work Package 4, highlighting the role of institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks in promoting sustainable trade and policy coherence.

This discussion paper has examined the role of institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks in promoting policy coherence for sustainable development. It focuses on the EU's agricultural trade policies and their alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and global environmental agreements. The analysis highlights several key findings regarding the effectiveness and challenges of the EU's current frameworks.

First, it highlights the importance of integrating SDGs into all policy-making levels to ensure coherence across trade, environmental, and development policies. While the EU has made significant progress in incorporating sustainability standards into its trade agreements, substantial gaps remain in achieving complete policy coherence. The need for an integrated *Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development (PCSD) Framework* is evident, as it could guide policymakers in aligning various policy areas with the SDGs and ensuring more consistent outcomes (OECD, 2016; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 7-8).

Second, the paper identifies several incoherencies and gaps within the EU's legal and regulatory frameworks, particularly concerning trade and environmental objectives. Despite the EU's commitments under the Paris Agreement and the European Green Deal, some policies—such as subsidies under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)—may inadvertently promote unsustainable agricultural practices. This inconsistency highlights the need for more binding commitments and enforceable clauses within trade agreements to ensure that environmental and climate objectives are not compromised (European Commission *EU Green Deal*, 2019; D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 6-7).

Third, the analysis reveals regional and sectoral variations in the application and impact of EU policies, often creating unequal opportunities and challenges for different countries and sectors. Countries with advanced institutional capacities, like Finland and Sweden, have effectively aligned their agricultural practices with EU sustainability goals. However, many developing countries face significant challenges due to inadequate infrastructure, limited technological access, and high compliance costs. Addressing these disparities is crucial for promoting more equitable and sustainable trade relationships (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 16-17).

6.2. Future Directions for Research and Policy Development

It identifies areas for future research and policy development, such as exploring the impacts of new trade agreements and assessing the effectiveness of policy coherence measurement mechanisms for achieving SDGs.

Given the identified gaps and challenges, several important directions exist for future research and policy development. One key area for further research is the development of more robust methods for assessing policy coherence. While impact assessments and Regulatory Impact Assessments (RIAs) are increasingly used to evaluate the potential effects of policies on sustainable development objectives, there is a need for more comprehensive tools that capture the full range of interactions between policies across different sectors and levels of governance. Future research could focus on developing *Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)* tools that better integrate social, economic, and environmental dimensions into policy assessments.

Another area for future research is the exploration of innovative approaches to capacity building and technical support for developing countries. The EU's capacity-building programs must be tailored to partner countries' specific needs and contexts, considering institutional capacities, socio-economic conditions, and local environmental challenges. Research could examine the effectiveness of different models of capacity building, such as South-South cooperation, public-private partnerships, and regional capacity-building networks, in enhancing compliance with EU standards and promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

There is also a need for more research on the role of voluntary sustainability standards (VSS) in promoting policy coherence and sustainable trade. While VSS such as Fair Trade and Organic certifications provide market-based incentives for sustainable practices, their impact on small-scale producers, women, and marginalised groups is not fully understood. Future research could explore how VSS can be better integrated into national and international legal frameworks and how they can promote more inclusive and equitable trade practices (D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 8).

Regarding policy development, the EU should consider revising its existing trade agreements to include more binding sustainability and human rights commitments. Introducing *Green Trade Agreements* that prioritise environmental and social objectives could serve as a model for future trade negotiations, ensuring that trade policies fully align with the SDGs and global environmental agreements. Policymakers should also explore the potential of establishing a *Policy Coherence Observatory* that tracks policy development across different domains and provides early warnings on potential incoherencies (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 15-16).

6.3. Final Remarks on Enhancing Policy Coherence and Sustainable Development

Enhancing policy coherence for sustainable development is not merely an aspiration but a necessity for the EU as it seeks to position itself as a global leader in sustainability. The findings of this paper highlight that achieving policy coherence requires a systemic and integrated approach that aligns trade, environmental, and development policies with the SDGs and global environmental agreements and thereby complements the findings from the analysis of agreements and political initiatives that make up the core trade policy of the EU (D4.2.). To achieve this, the EU must invest in more robust legal and institutional frameworks that provide clear guidelines, enforceable commitments, and effective coordination mechanisms (OECD, 2016; D4.3 *The Political Economy of Trade Regimes*, 10-12).

The EU must also recognise the importance of inclusive and participatory policy-making in promoting policy coherence. Engaging a wide range of stakeholders—including civil society, the private sector, and marginalised groups—in the policy process can help ensure that policies are more responsive to diverse needs and contexts. This participatory approach is critical for identifying potential incoherencies and gaps early in the policy cycle and for building broad-based support for sustainable development objectives (D4.4 *Report Webinar' Policy Coherence*).

Moreover, the EU should adopt a more proactive approach to capacity building and technical support for developing countries. This includes not only providing financial resources but also facilitating knowledge exchange, fostering regional cooperation, and supporting the development of local institutional capacities. By enhancing the capacity of partner countries to comply with EU standards and benefit from trade opportunities, the EU can promote more equitable and sustainable trade relationships that align with its broader development goals.

In conclusion, the path to achieving policy coherence for sustainable development is complex and requires concerted efforts at all levels of governance, especially concerning the EU's trade engagements with third countries. The EU is critical in setting sustainable trade policy standards and ensuring its legal and institutional frameworks support global sustainability objectives. By addressing the identified gaps and incoherencies, particularly with respect to intellectual property and human rights, strengthening policy coordination, and promoting fair and inclusive trade practices, the EU can enhance its impact on sustainable development and contribute to a more equitable and sustainable world (D4.1 *Synthesis of Findings*, 17-19).

The recommendations outlined in this paper provide a roadmap for policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders to enhance the coherence of EU policies and

frameworks. While challenges are ahead, there are also significant opportunities for innovation, collaboration, and transformative change. The EU must seize these opportunities to demonstrate its commitment to sustainable development and set a positive example for other regions and countries (European Commission, 2020; D4.2 *Discussion Paper on Mechanisms*, 12-13).

Ultimately, achieving policy coherence for sustainable development is not just about aligning policies but creating a more integrated, inclusive, and sustainable approach to global governance. This requires shifting from a siloed and fragmented approach to a more holistic and systemic perspective that recognises the interconnections between different policy areas and the need for coordinated action. Moving in this direction, the EU can help build a more sustainable and resilient global economy that benefits all (OECD, 2023).

7. References

1. **Carbone, M. (2008).** Mission Impossible: The European Union and Policy Coherence for Development. *Journal of European Integration*, 30(3), 323-342.
2. **European Commission. (2019).** The European Green Deal. Available at: [European Commission Website](#).
3. **European Commission. (2020).** Farm to Fork Strategy. Available at: [European Commission Website](#).
4. **Mayer, F., & Gereffi, G. (2017).** Regulation and Economic Globalisation: Prospects and Limits of Private Governance. *Business and Politics*, 12(3), 1-25.
5. **Meadowcroft, J. (2007).** Who is in Charge here? Governance for Sustainable Development in a Complex World. *Journal of Environmental Policy and Planning*, 9(3-4), 299-314.
6. **Nilsson, M., Griggs, D., & Visbeck, M. (2012).** Policy: Map the interactions between Sustainable Development Goals. *Nature*, 534(7607), 320-322.
7. **Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2023).** Driving Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development. Accelerating Progress on the SDGs. Paris: OECD Publishing.
8. **Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2016).** Better Policies for Sustainable Development. A New Framework for Policy Coherence. Paris: OECD Publishing.
9. **Young, A. R., & Peterson, J. (2013).** "We care about you, but ...": The politics of EU trade policy and development. *Cambridge Review of International Affairs*, 26(3), 497-518.
10. **Collste, D., Pedercini, M., & Cornell, S. E. (2017).** Policy coherence to achieve the SDGs: using integrated simulation models to assess effective policies. *Sustainability science*, 12, 921-931.
11. **Picciotto, R. (2005).** The evaluation of policy coherence for development. *Evaluation*, 11(3), 311-330.
12. **King, M., Keijzer, N., Spierings, E., & Matthews, A. (2012).** Measuring policy coherence for development. *Maastricht: European Centre for Development Policy Management*.

13. Documents from the MATS Project:

- **D4.1:** Synthesis of Findings on the Impact of Institutional Frameworks from the Set of 15 Case Studies. <https://zenodo.org/records/13736367>
- **D4.2:** Discussion Paper on Mechanisms that Can Ensure that EU Policies are Coherent with SDGs. <https://zenodo.org/records/10441661>
- **D4.3:** The Political Economy of Trade Regimes: Final Report. <https://zenodo.org/records/10450456>
- **D4.4:** Report on Webinar' Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development'. <https://zenodo.org/records/10925277>